

MODELING OF THERMAL CYCLING DAMAGE IN
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Previous models for thermal cycling damage in metal matrix composites including our recent one are critically reviewed. They are aimed at modeling of the dimensional change in as-thermally-cycled MMCs. Then, the thermal cycling damages that have not been modeled are discussed and possible modeling of these damages is suggested.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) are emerging as a new class of structural material in high temperature applications such as reciprocal and turbine engines. The objective of using an MMC system over the existing metal alloys (or superalloys) is to obtain the higher use temperature and higher specific mechanical properties which are important requirements for moving engine components. Thus, the target use temperature range of MMCs overlaps that of superalloys at the low temperature end and that of ceramics and ceramic matrix composites at the high temperature end [1]. In order to better design an MMC component for high temperature application, one must assess a complete picture of its mechanical behavior in a high temperature environment. The most important high temperature environment that a candidate MMC will presumably experience includes exposure at high temperature under constant load (creep) and thermal cycling. Despite the importance of the

mechanical behavior of MMCs in such thermal environments, few studies have been made on the damage modes and the damage accumulation process of MMCs in creep and/or thermal cycling environments. The basic understanding of the mechanical behavior of a candidate MMC under these thermal environments is that the reinforcement phase (short or continuous fiber) contributes to the increase in the stiffness and strength of the MMC at high temperatures and to the reduction in the steady state (second stage) creep rate, i.e., improvement in the creep resistance; but in a thermal cycling environment the reinforcing fibers become obstacles in promoting micro-damages which will reduce the residual mechanical properties and contribute to the dimensional change of the as-thermally cycled MMC.

Thermal cycling between low (T_{\min}) and high temperature (T_{\max}) is known to cause significant degradation for most of the MMC systems [2-16]. The degradation of as-thermally cycled MMCs is attributed to the mismatch of the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTEs) between the matrix metal and fiber, and also to the reaction products at the matrix-fiber interfaces. Previous studies [2-16] determined that these factors result in the microscopic degradation in MMCs and are usually associated with the matrix-fiber interfaces. This microscopic degradation leads to a reduction in the residual mechanical properties and a dimensional change of the as-thermally cycled MMCs. Some attempts have been made to model the dimensional change of as-thermally cycled MMCs, i.e., for a continuous fiber MMC system [3-5,20], short fiber MMC [19], and MMC under both thermal cycling and constant stress [17,18].

In this paper, we will review the existing models for the dimensional change in as-thermally cycled MMCs in an effort to have a clear picture of the advantages and limitations of each model. Then, possible improvements in these models will be discussed, followed by a suggestion on the modeling of the other damages associated with thermal cycling of MMCs.

MODELS FOR DIMENSIONAL CHANGE

Dimensional change in as-thermally cycled MMCs has been modeled by several groups. For convenience, these models are grouped into the following categories:

- (1) Garmong model [3,4]
- (2) Wakashima et al. model [5,6,18]
- (3) Min model [20]
- (4) Derby model [17]
- (5) Taya-Mori model [19]

Of the above models, the Wakashima et al. model [18] and the Derby model [17] are aimed at the dimensional change under both thermal cycling and constant stress, while the others at that wider thermal cycling only.

The Garmong model [3] is based on the assumption that the state of stress and strain in each phase of an MMC is one-dimensional, the matrix metal obeys an elastic/plastic/creep law while the fiber remains elastic, and the matrix-fiber interface is perfectly bonded. The results of the parametric study based on the Garmong model indicate that permanent strain per cycle Δe decreases rapidly as the number of cycles N increases, converging to uniform value beyond several cycles, and Δe increases as fiber volume fraction f increases [4], which is in agreement with the experimental results reported in [2]. The creep law used in the Garmong model is of the power-law type where several material constants in the creep law of the unreinforced matrix metal must be known. Though some of the material constants in the creep law are quite sensitive on the creep rate, the accuracy of their values is often poor, leading to the crude approximation of the dimensional change. Garmong showed the extension of the one-dimensional stress model to the case of isotropic to two- and three-dimensional stress states [3]. However, the above extension to the isotropic three-dimensional case seems trivial, since the dimensional change in the isotropic composite, for example, spherical particle MMC, is expected to be zero. Namely, the dimensional change of as-thermally cycled MMC is expected to increase with the fiber aspect ratio l/d [19]. The extension of the Garmong model to the non-isotropic three-dimensional stress state is considered straightforward and useful for a short fiber MMC. In fact, the above extension has been incorporated in part into our model [19].

Based on the experimental finding on the sliding of the matrix-fiber interface in continuous tungsten fiber/copper composite (W/Cu composite), Wakashima and his co-workers constructed a simple, yet accurate model to

predict the dimensional change [5]. The Wakashima et al. model is similar to the Garmong model in the sense that the state of stress is one-dimensional, thus suited for continuous fiber MMC, but it is based on an assumption different from that in the Garmong model. Namely, the matrix-fiber interface consists of a thin viscous layer, while the matrix is an elastic/perfectly plastic solid. The Wakashima et al. model, based on the viscous interface layer, predicts that the final dimensional change decreases with the increase in fiber volume fraction f , which is opposite to the prediction based on the Garmong model and ours, but is in agreement with the experimental results of a W/Cu composite. This is because the interface in W/Cu composite is known to be compatible. Namely, no detrimental compounds are formed at the interface, thus the behavior of the interface at elevated temperatures can be described approximately by a viscous layer, as in the Wakashima et al. model. Despite the above success of the Wakashima et al. model, it may not be applicable to other cases, such as MMCs with incompatible interface and short fiber MMC, where the matrix creep will be dominant at T_{\max} . Wakashima et al. [18] has recently extended the above model to the case of thermal cycling and tensile loading where the accelerated dimensional change, called "superplasticity," is known to occur. The extended model can predict a linear relation between the dimensional change and applied tensile stress σ , in good agreement with the experimental results of Al-Al₃N₄ eutectic composites [18].

Min [20] has recently simulated the strain-ratchetting phenomena in a continuous graphite fiber/aluminum composite subjected to thermal cycling by using the model that Min and his co-worker developed [13,20]. The Min model is based on the assumption that the stresses in a composite are two-dimensional (plane stress) and the matrix metal is elastic/plastic solid where the plasticity constitutive equation is given in incremental form, thus, it can accommodate any plasticity model. However, the Min model does not account for creep in the matrix, nor for viscous motion at the matrix-fiber interface. Hence, the Min model appears to belong to a standard elastic/plastic solid model which has been used extensively to study the mechanical behavior of metal matrix composites at room temperature or relatively low temperatures. The Min model can predict the transient behavior of the permanent strain per cycle $\Delta\epsilon$ during the first several cycles [20], which is in agreement with the analytical results by Garmong [4]. Due to the plane stress

assumption, the Min model can easily be extended to account for the case of a laminated composite. Despite the above advantages, the Min model may not be able to predict the dimensional change in an MMC that is subjected to thermal cycling between T_{\min} and relatively high T_{\max} when the matrix creep is expected to take place.

Superplasticity has been known for some class of metal alloys. It is quite recent that some types of MMCs also are found to exhibit such superplasticity if they are subjected to both thermal cycling and constant tensile stress (creep) [16,18]. Derby has recently proposed a simple three-dimensional model to predict the dimensional change of as-thermally cycled and creep loaded short fiber MMC [17]. The Derby model assumes that all short fibers are aligned along a specified direction and the matrix is elastic/plastic/creep solid. The prediction by the Derby model agrees reasonably well with the experimental results of Wu and Sherby [16]. As applied stress is reduced to zero in the Derby model, i.e., corresponding to thermal cycling only, the Derby model predicts zero dimensional change, which is in disagreement with the experimental results of Patterson and Taya on a short fiber MMC [14].

Motivated by the experimental results of Patterson and Taya [14], Taya and Mori have recently proposed a model for the prediction of the dimensional change in as-thermally cycled short fiber MMCs [19]. The Taya-Mori model is based on the following assumptions:

- (1) at T_{\max} the stress relaxation occurs by the matrix creep and the diffusion at the matrix-fiber interface
- (2) at T_{\min} the stress relaxation occurs by the plastic deformation of the matrix.

The Eshelby type model [21,22] was used in the Taya-Mori model to calculate the average matrix stress at different stages (cooling and heating). The dimensional change predicted by this model agrees reasonably well with the experiment [14], as seen from Table 1. It should be noted in Table 1 that the agreement along the thickness direction is excellent, but it is poor in the other two directions, i.e., the length (L) and width (W) of the plate. This discrepancy along the L and W directions is expected, since in the actual short fiber MMC (SiC

whisker/2124 aluminum) [14], short fibers are misoriented in the L-W plane though the majority are along the L direction, and they are all perpendicular to the thickness direction. Whereas, in the Taya-Mori model, all short fibers are assumed to be aligned along the L direction.

TABLE 1

Comparison between the experimental and analytical results of the dimensional change of as-thermally cycled SiC w/2124 Al.

Dimensional Change at 1000 Cycles with $T_{max} = 673K$		
Directions of the Dimensional Change	Experimental Results [14]	Analytical Results [19]
Length (L)	0.055	0.158
Width (W)	0.020	-0.079
Thickness (TH)	-0.079	-0.079

The dimensional change of as-thermally cycled aligned short fiber MMC predicted by the Taya-Mori model was found to increase with fiber volume fraction f and fiber aspect ratio l/d .

DISCUSSION

Among the analytical results obtained by the above five models, the effect of fiber volume fraction f on the dimensional change Δe appears to be controversial. Namely, the models by Garmong, and Taya and Mori predict that Δe increases with f , while the Wakashima et al. model predicts the opposite. Since each model was developed with application to specific MMC system, the validity of these models must be carefully evaluated. As discussed in the previous section, MMCs can be grouped into two types, MMCs with compatible interface and those with incompatible interface. Examples of the former and latter types are W/Cu composite and graphite fiber/aluminum composite or generally ceramic fiber/metal composites. Thus, the Wakashima et al. model is best suited for continuous fiber MMC with compatible interface, while the Taya-Mori model is reasonably accurate in predicting the dimensional change of a short fiber MMC with incompatible interface.

When a MMC with incompatible interface experiences a severe thermal environment such as thermal cycling, the matrix-fiber interface may be partially debonded. Such partially debonded interface is expected to grow as a number of cycles increases [15]. None of the above models have dealt with the simulation of the initiation and growth of such interface debonding. In the case of a short fiber MMC, short fibers are often misoriented due to the processing. The effect of this fiber misorientation on the thermal cycling damage remains to be investigated. A possible direction in the modeling of the damage observed in as-thermally cycled MMC is to employ the concept of coated fiber composite [23] where the coating can be envisaged as "interface damage" such as debonded interface, or that of sliding inclusion [24].

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